

Opportunities and Risks of LLM-enabled Tools and Automations

* Required

Your information

1

Participant ID *

2

Which area are you working in?

- Automotive- Autonomous Vehicles or ADAS Functions
- Automotive- Other safety relevant applications
- Automotive- Non safety relevant functions
- Other

3

How long have you been working in this domain? (including relevant PhD years)

4

Which one is true about your company:

- OEM
- Software supplier
- Other

5

Please specify your role:

- Manager or Product Owner
- Software Developer
- System or Function Developer
- Verification and Validation Engineer
- Safety Engineer
- Other

6

Which case is true in your case:

- Providing inputs to the programmers (E.g., requirements, software architectures, ...)
- Writing Codes
- Reviewing Codes
- Receiver of softwares (e.g., Testing, integration of software with other components, ...)
- Other

7

Project Description: "Assuring Safety for Rapid and Continuous Deployment for Autonomous Driving" (ASSERTED) is a research project that started in November 2021 and funded by Sweden's Innovation Agency (Diarienummer: 2021-02585). Our research goal is to explore methods for coping better with the safety of autonomously driving vehicles for rapid and continuous development and deployment. The project is funded by Sweden's Innovation Agency (Vinnova) and is a collaboration between Volvo Cars, Zenseact, and Chalmers.

Consent Confirmation: I voluntarily agree to participate in this study, and I understand that my answers will be anonymized, handled according to GDPR, and may be used for research purposes within the ASSERTED project. By ticking this box, I confirm that I have read and understood the *ASSERTED – Informed Consent Form (Oct. 2025)*. *

- I confirm my informed consent
- I decline to participate

Your experience with using AI tools

Context: In our study AI is referred to LLM-based tools

8

Do you have any experience with Large Language Models in your daily tasks? *

Yes

No

9

If yes, which Model and for what task?

10

What are the potential / advantages of these tools?

11

What are the limitations / disadvantages of these tools?

LLM-Driven Knowledge Support

12

What do you see as the main strengths / limitations / concerns of existing third-party LLM tools (e.g., Chat GPT, Gemini, Copilot) when applied to your work?

13

What errors might occur in this use case?

14

What impact could those errors have on the final artifact?

15

Are there detection or mitigation mechanisms in place to catch such errors?

16

Any other comments or concerns?

VLM-Based Runtime Monitoring and Event Detection

17

What errors might occur in this use case?

18

What impact could those errors have on the final artifact?

19

Are there detection or mitigation mechanisms in place to catch such errors?

20

Any other comments or concerns?

LLM-Driven Code Generation and Verification

Generate Fast, Eliminate Fast

25

What errors might occur in this use case?

26

What impact could those errors have on the final artifact?

27

Are there detection or mitigation mechanisms in place to catch such errors?

28

How do you evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of this process?

29

Any other comments or concerns?

AI in My Role: Opportunities and Risks

30

What impact do you think AI tools will have on your job?

- Make my work easier / more efficient
- Take over boring or repetitive tasks
- Might reduce parts of my role
- Could replace my role entirely
- I won't use it, or it should be forbidden in my tasks
- Other

31

What tasks would you want an AI tool to help you with at work?

32

Any final comment?

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